

CROSSING GENDER. SOCIOLOGY MEETS OTHER DISCIPLINES

GENDER STUDIES RESEARCH NETWORK - ITALIAN SOCIOLOGICAL ASSOCIATION

BOOK OF ABSTRACT

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Introduction¹

Since its first formalization by Gayle Rubin (1975), gender has emerged as an increasingly relevant key to observing and understanding the contemporary world and its change (Connell 1987, Bourdieu 1999). Indeed, among the most relevant recent social transformations are to be counted precisely those pertaining to the specific weight of this identifying category for individuals and groups (Risman 2004, Ruspini 2023).

The culture on gender is progressively entering the public debate also thanks to the possibilities of representation and "taking the floor" offered by digital media and, in particular, by social media (Farci, Scarcelli, 2022) and has become the subject of political decisions on aspects and issues that affect personal rights (civil unions, parental leave, etc.) from a perspective of overcoming gender dualism (Connell 1995, Butler 1999). Meanwhile, sexual identity has begun to be socially perceived as culturally defined, regulated and symbolized (Gregersen 2022). It follows that reflecting on the dimension of gender and how it exerts a critical function in the domains of social life - from education, to socialization or language - as cultural constructs through which gender is concretized - is the task not only of a single discipline, but of the social sciences in dialogue with other disciplines (Corbisiero, Nocenzi, eds., 2022).

Each discipline encounters gender as a strategic object of study in the prevailing sphere in which it operates, but, at the same time, any social fact reflects in a more or less direct way the transformations related to gender, its multiple representations and explanations, diversified in synchronic and diachronic terms, on the micro and macro, material and symbolic planes. The gender pay gap phenomenon, for example, affects the conditions of female workers by investigating law and business economics with questions about a patently discriminatory form. This, however, must be read in an integrated way with the socio-anthropological dynamics of power management connected to the emerging capitalist mode of production (Engels 1884) and access to material and relational resources, of sedimentation in history from the transition from nomadism to horticultural societies (O'Kelly and Carney 1986, Magda I., Cukrowska-Torzewska E. 2019). In recent years, moreover, great attention is paid by the scientific community to the issue of gender variance, and to all the subjective conditions of those who do not identify with a binary view of gender. The latter constitute an aspect still little investigated by sociology and, therefore, it will be crucial to engage with those expert knowledge that within other disciplines (including clinical psychology, cultural anthropology, and medicine) have begun to accrue expertise decades ago (Monro, 2019). And the connection between fields and disciplines could follow for several more steps.

¹ The Introduction contains the text of the call for papers for participation in the conference: the scientific project is proposed in line with the activities conducted by the AIS Gender Studies Research Network.

Despite the obvious transversality of gender, there is a struggle to apply its holistic property, except in frameworks such as the one outlined in the 2030 Agenda (UN 2015) in which goals such as No. 5 (gender equality) and No. 10 (reducing inequality) are prerequisites to the realization of all 17 Sustainable Development Goals. The outcomes of this “strategic resistance” are now tangible, and the ineffectiveness of responses to dramatic problems such as gender-based violence - when they aim at specialization and not integration of expertise and disciplinary visions to counter, study and prevent it - is one of many examples (Brink et al, 2021). Indeed, multi- and interdisciplinary approaches are gradually being joined by trans-disciplinary approaches whose different types of knowledge production for social change are based not only on the integration of knowledge from different disciplines (interdisciplinarity), but also on the inclusion of values, knowledge, know-how and skills from non-academic sources (Klein, 2017). This implies “mutual learning between science and society, (...) embodying a mission of science with society rather than for society” (Seidl et al. 2013). Therefore, it builds on established methods to produce “reliable knowledge”, but goes beyond that to generate “socially sound knowledge” as is increasingly required of science in applied research projects” (Green Deal, NRP).

The conference is proposed as an opportunity for discussion and debate, aimed at the scientific community, the sociological community, and all other disciplines, on the topic of gender transversality. The proposal for conceptual and/or research papers is also addressed to the world of professions, representatives of civil society and associations.

Some of the cognitive questions that may animate the debate, although not exhaustive, are:

Ø How can gender be defined in light of its transversality? What are the epistemological difficulties? What are its manifestations?

Ø Does the transversality of gender, which requires a form of humility on the part of the researcher in addressing issues and not presuming to “know exactly what the problem is”, constitute a challenge to the disciplines?

Ø What is the role of sociology and, more broadly, that of the social sciences in heuristics on gender? What, specifically, toward other disciplines?

Ø Is a multi- or interdisciplinary approach still appropriate for the study of a research object when it is related to gender? What are the strengths and what are the weaknesses?

Ø How to do transdisciplinary research on gender or social facts characterized by this factor?

Ø What added value and/or critical issues does adopt the transdisciplinary approach in gender research propose?

Ø How can gender be the common goal of different and rarely integrated disciplines?

Ø Are there disciplinary areas that can integrate with each other more successfully in analyzing the gender factor? If yes, what facilitates their coming together? If not, what are the major impediments?

Ø How do we achieve that integration between academic and conventional knowledge that characterizes transdisciplinary studies and that gender-related issues require to be better understood?

Ø Can gender promote mutual learning processes between science and society that embody a mission of science with society rather than for society?

Ø What resistance does science itself face to cross-fertilization in gender studies?

Ø Can the intersectionality approach enrich the debate on gender cross-fertilization by bringing in new visions and new empirical evidence?

Ø Is it possible to think of a new paradigm for research from gender across disciplines (transdisciplinarity) that creates and applies knowledge produced with stakeholders while maximizing its social impact?

Building on these questions and thematic cues, the call invites proposals with a theoretical and/or empirical slant that intend to measure up to one or more of the above questions. Proposals from transdisciplinary research teams and Ph.D. and research fellows will be particularly welcome.

Submissions may be articulated in relation and interconnectedness in the following thematic areas:

- Gender, sexuality and identity
- Gender representation and social change
- Socialization to gender and educational processes
- Gender in media representation
- Health and gender
- Violence and secondary victimization
- Migration processes from a gender perspective

- Gender as a goal of sustainable development
- Gender in multicultural societies
- Gender pay gap and other forms of asymmetry in the labour market
- Women's bio capital and the use of the body
- Gender and power
- Gender in the academy
- Gender studies and intersectionality

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Panel Methodological Challenges

Using Intersectional and Gender Data in R&I to Create Real Impact: the CNR's Data Warehouse

Sara Marini, Nicolò Marchesini, Cloe Mirenda, Loredana Cerbara, Daniela Luzi, Enrico Malandrino, Fabrizio Pecoraro, Lucio Pisacane, National Research Council of Italy (CNR)

Introduction

This contribution aims to discuss the administrative data relevance in the analysis of intersectional and gender dimensions in research organizations. In the last decade, data-driven policies in research organisations have gained momentum thanks to four pushing factors: EU policy on gender equality (including the gender equality plans –GEP- design), the Data Feminist (DF) approach, and the raising of the Open Science (OS) movement and Open Data (OP) requirements.

The contribution discusses these four pushing factors and builds upon the experience of the EU funded project MINDtheGEPs to illustrate a structural change in the data collection, update and analyses of administrative data at the Italian National Research Council (CNR). MINDtheGEPs supported the implementation of the GEP where an interdisciplinary team implemented a new data warehouse for managing and using administrative data of the almost ten thousand workers at CNR.

1. The driving forces for the realisation of the DWH

1.1. GEP at EU level

Gender equality is a core value of the EU (TFEU, 2012, Art.8) and is currently one of the six top policy priorities for research and innovation of the European Commission. As such, it is integrated into the EU Framework Programmes (FP) for research and innovation and into the agenda for European Research Area. In the current FP, gender equality in the teams' composition and research content became a crucial dimension incorporated as a prerequisite in the eligibility of research organisations applying for the funding scheme. Hence, since 2022, GEPs as organisational strategy documents have been required to participate in FP. GEPs must be evidence-based, using sex or gender-disaggregated data from all staff categories. This data informs GEP objectives, targets, indicators, and ongoing evaluations, with annual reporting. GEPs serve as catalysts for improving gender data collection and utilizing existing administrative data for better measurement and evaluation. Studies show that the most effective interventions are context-specific and rely on robust data collection processes. This approach has been crucial for understanding the impacts of gender equality interventions in R&I (Palmer et al., 2019).

1.2. Data Science and Data Ethics informed by intersectional feminist approach: Data Feminism

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Regarding data, the MINDtheGEPs refers to DF, defined by D'Ignazio and Klein (2020) as an approach that integrates the principles of intersectional feminism at every stage of the data life-cycle. In addition to sex disaggregation, recognize the gender dimension, considering power imbalances and lack of representation as structural elements of the entire process (Broussard, 2023).

DF acknowledges the non-neutrality of data, which is influenced by those who conceived and analysed it: the definition of the dataset and the analytical model serves as a means to exercise power (Irani, 2019). It is essential to create and utilize data that do not solely reflect the realities of white, able-bodied, affluent men but also represent the diversity of experiences, economic capabilities, and identities, ranging from women with disabilities to LGBTQIA+ individuals. This also involves making visible the labour of the numerous individuals involved in data science.

DF aims to promote lasting and equitable social change that addresses discrimination arising, in contextual ways and measures, from the intersection of various axes of discrimination (Crenshaw, 1989); to inspire, monitor and evaluate policies, and to measure their progress. For an effective re-examination of work paradigms, data gaps must be a central focus in research and the planning of contexts.

Furthermore, we also propose considering the socio-technical and -productive characteristics of data systems defining processes and employment opportunities.

1.3. Open Science and Open Data

Contextual factors that have contributed to a cultural and institutional change toward the disclosure of information can be traced in two parallel but often overlapping movements: OS and OD. The first one can be considered the evolution of the Open access movement (Guédon et al., 2019), which gradually evolved in terms of the types of information considered (from scientific journals to data), technologies (from repositories to scientific infrastructures) and policies (from re-use licenses to mandates for free access of scientific information). In addition, OS promotes a system change that facilitates creation, collaboration and knowledge sharing during the entire research process (Vicente-Saez, Martinez-Fuentes, 2018).

If the principles of OS can be traced back to the epistemic discussion on the role of science (Merton, 1968), the OD movement has more recent social requirements being based on the right of free access to information and on the extension of the “right to knowledge which is a basic principle for democracy” (European Commission, 2009).

OD, or more precisely open governmental data, originates from public institutional bodies and intends to facilitate the free availability of data “collected, produced, reproduced, and disseminated within the exercise of a public task or a service of general interest” (European Commission, 2009). Besides national initiatives, worth mentioning are the European directives that provide Member states with the legal and technological framework that facilitates data re-use for purposes other than the ones they were originally collected for. The most recent directive (European Parliament, Council of the EU, 2019), also includes research performing organisations and research funding organisations within the public sector and specifically refers to their production of research data and open access. Therefore, research institutions should make both research data and data originating from their administrative process freely available for reuse. Common aims for the disclosure of information are transparency, accountability and public participation, while specifically for the scientific sector there is the need to facilitate research reproducibility and validation.

2. The limits of administrative data

Along with factors that support the collection of gender-related administrative data, it is vital to recognize the legal boundaries governing such collection. These boundaries are defined by national and international legislation, which are crucial for regulating data practices. At the European level, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Regulation (EU) 2016/679) serves as the flagship legislation concerning personal data. In Italy, relevant laws include the Workers' Statute (Law No. 300 of 1970) and the Privacy Code (Legislative Decree No. 196 of 2003). GDPR (Article 9) and the Italian Privacy Code (Article 26) restrict processing sensitive data unless a lawful basis exists, such as explicit consent or a legal obligation. Furthermore, Article 8 of the Italian Workers' Statute prohibits employers from collecting information irrelevant to an employee's professional abilities, limiting gender-related data collection.

These legal frameworks share common principles regarding the ethical and legal treatment of gender-related data, focusing on privacy protection, data minimization, and anti-discrimination. All three frameworks classify gender data as sensitive or special category data needing enhanced protection due to its potential impact on individuals' privacy and dignity. Before processing gender information, a lawful basis is required under each framework. GDPR (Articles 6 and 9) mandates a lawful basis like explicit consent or legitimate interest, while the Italian Privacy Code and Workers' Statute reinforce this need by restricting access to non-essential personal information. Ethical standards from the Declaration of Helsinki, Belmont Report, and ISO/IEC 29100 Privacy Framework highlight individual rights, privacy, transparency, and fairness regarding sensitive data handling. Although these standards arise from medical research and information technology, they are highly applicable to analysing administrative gender data. In summary, organizations must ensure that findings from gender-related data analysis promote fairness and inclusivity, avoiding discrimination and maintaining accountability through periodic audits and ethical oversight.

3. The CNR data warehouse

The need for a digital tool to query administrative data with a gender perspective at the CNR arises from the requirement to implement the GEPs under Horizon Europe. These plans must be customized to fit the organization's specific characteristics and measurable goals. A comprehensive data repository is essential for analysing staff demographics, recruitment, career progression, decision-making bodies, work-life balance, and scientific output. Gender budgeting plays a crucial role by providing insights into gender-related aspects at specific times. To address this need, a working group composed of research personnel and central administrative staff is integrating the CNR's databases, initially designed for administrative purposes, while leveraging the organization's internal expertise. This working group aims to develop a data warehouse (DWH) that allows continuous uploading of new or updated data sources. The goal is to create a coherent and inclusive database to facilitate Gender Budgeting when necessary and help define targeted, measurable actions under the GEP.

The GEP involves the collection and analysis of data from the micro and meso context, preparatory to its design. For this reason, work on the development of the DWH began in 2021. Following the approval of the GEP, in 2022, the CNR produces an annual Gender Budgeting report that provides a dynamic overview of the gender distribution among various components within the organization (research staff, technical and administrative staff, management, fellows, and scholarship recipients), as well as the participation of women and men in the leadership bodies and in the scientific network scattered in the territories.

In the DWH of the CNR, the operational information systems of the institution are represented. The DWH collects data available from various information sources and stores it in autonomous structures; it also gathers historical data, allowing for a diachronic reading of the data in its evolution, which is essential for longitudinal analyses (Table 1). Data that were previously unconnected are thus integrated, enabling cross-sectional analyses and producing, if needed, reports related to demographics, competition commissions, applications for subsidies, and external funding.

Table 1 – Current data and information resources of the CNR DWH

Areas of interest	Description	Sources
Employed Staff Demographics 2016-2020	Research staff, technologists, administrative personnel, and technical staff.	Personnel Data Mart
Employed staff	Categorized by profile (researcher, technologist, technician, administrative, private employment contract), level, department, sex, and age.	Personnel Data Mart
Fellows and Scholars personnel	Research fellows and scholarship holders categorized by assignment, department, profile, level, sex, age, and assignment amount.	Personnel Data Mart Accounting Data Mart
Leaves	Employed staff by type and duration of leave (hourly and daily).	Personnel Data Mart
Territorial structure	Employed staff by type of territorial level (Institute, Department, Research Area) and location (Municipality, main or secondary headquarters, or research units at third parties).	Personnel Data Mart Accounting Data Mart
Projects, contracts, and funding	List of active projects by Principal Investigator, territorial structure, kind and amount of funding.	Project - Accounting Personnel Data Mart
Publications and patents	Publications and patents with at least one CNR author.	Research Products and Protection DPI Intellectual property rights Data Mart

To complete the list of sources of information input of the DWH, some sources still require preparatory work to be integrated into the DWH, such as the economic balance sheet or the doctoral students hosted by the institution.

4. Current and future challenges

While the development of the CNR's DWH is still underway, several limitations have already been identified. These limitations stem from the theoretical framework of reference, which invites further discussion and investigation.

At present, the organization's approach to OS and FAIR data is not fully integrated into the tool. The decision to base its architecture on the organization's specific characteristics and existing skill set has resulted in the use of licensed software. This choice brings about certain limitations typical of traditional software, such as an annual fee, limited customization options to meet unique needs, and a concentration of technological skills among a small number of individuals capable of managing the system. Despite these challenges, there are ongoing efforts to improve the Interoperability and Reusability of the organization's internal data by enhancing communication between various information sources, aiming to unlock the full potential of the information available.

However, the system's limited openness is evident in access to the tool. In contrast to the collaborative and transparent nature of OS, the current DWH is only accessible to authorized internal staff for strategic administrative purposes. There has yet to be a developed method for the organization's staff or external stakeholders to access the data openly.

Conclusions

The experience with the DWH presents several challenges that need to be addressed for its improvement and effectiveness. At the organizational level, it is essential to involve administrative offices that are not yet part of the process to broaden the data perspective and thoroughly analyse gender inequalities. Furthermore, access to the tool should be extended to all personnel within the organization rather than being limited to authorized individuals only, as outlined in the OS framework. Additionally, a series of actions should be implemented to encourage top management to use the tool for planning organizational strategies across various managerial areas. At the cultural level, there is a need to promote the use of these data for research purposes, with the aim of fostering dialogue with leadership regarding policy formulation.

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Come analizzare la cyberviolenza di genere? Primi risultati e riflessioni metodologiche da una ricerca in corso

Tatiana Motterle, Angela M. Toffanin, CNR-IRPPS

In questo contributo presentiamo una riflessione critica sui primi risultati del progetto Social representations of cyber-violence against women and girls: advancing knowledge on an under-conceptualized issue, che analizza la violenza di genere mediata dalle tecnologia digitali (cyber-GBV), con l'obiettivo chiave di esplorare quelle pratiche che, agite online, si situano in maniera esplicita a cavallo (e potenzialmente ridefiniscono i confini) tra la dimensione pubblica e quella privata, tra le pratiche che sono riconosciute e nominate come violente e quelle non violente, nell'interazione tra le dimensioni di vita online e offline (FRA 2018, Jenkins, Ford, Green 2006). Il progetto coinvolge tre unità di ricerca (Università di Bologna, Università del Salento, Cnr-Irpps) e indaga nello specifico: le rappresentazioni della cyber-GBV tra giovani e adolescenti; le rappresentazioni della cyber-GBV nei media e nei telegiornali italiani, con un focus specifico sui prodotti mediatici e sugli ambienti online rivolti a giovani e adolescenti; le rappresentazioni della cyber-GBV in documenti politici, programmi di prevenzione e campagne di sensibilizzazione promossi a livello nazionale e analizzati applicando la metodologia della critical frame analysis (Verloo, 2007) e adottando una prospettiva comparativa a livello europeo.

Condividiamo innanzitutto i risultati dell'analisi delle policy narratives europee, italiane, spagnole e francesi, che ha come obiettivo quello di comprendere come questo fenomeno sia concettualizzato, definito e affrontato nei vari contesti. La nostra analisi si concentra sull'importanza dell'intersezionalità all'interno dei quadri politici e degli interventi programmatici (Collins, 2019; Crenshaw, 2017), valutando inoltre in

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